
The Influence of Social Media Influencers on Purchase Intention Mediated by Trust in User Content of Ruangguru Application in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the influence of Social Media Influencers on the purchase intention of Ruangguru application users mediated by trust in social media content. The research method uses a quantitative approach with data collection techniques through online questionnaires distributed to 410 junior high and high school students in Indonesia. Data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Squares (PLS) with the help of SmartPLS 4.0 software. The results showed that Social Media Influencers had a significant effect on trust in social media content ($\beta = 0.318$, $p < 0.05$) and purchase intention ($\beta = 0.368$, $p < 0.05$). Trust in content was also shown to mediate the relationship between Social Media Influencers and purchase intention ($\beta = 0.063$, $p < 0.05$). Influencer attributes such as informative value, entertainment, expertise, trustworthiness, attractiveness, and similarity positively influence audience trust, which ultimately drives purchase intention. The implications of this study provide guidance for Ruangguru in selecting credible and relevant influencers to increase user trust and purchase intention. In addition, these findings enrich the digital marketing literature by confirming the mediating role of trust in the relationship between influencers and consumer behavior.

KEYWORDS: Social Media Influencers, purchase intention, trust in content, Ruangguru

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of digital technology has changed various aspects of people's lives, especially in the way of communication and social interaction. Social media has become one of the main platforms used by people to communicate, share information, and as a means of digital marketing. In today's digital era, social media not only functions as a communication tool, but has also become a basic need for many people, especially the younger generation who are very familiar with the use of the internet and digital devices. Indonesia, as one of the countries with significant growth in internet and social media users, recorded more than 185 million internet users in 2024, with a penetration rate reaching 66.5% of the total population (Dewi, 2021) .

Data shows that the majority of Indonesian youth use the internet primarily for entertainment and accessing social media, while internet usage for productive activities such as online learning is still relatively low (Tianto et al., 2022) . This indicates a shift in internet usage patterns among young people after face-to-face learning was reinstated post-pandemic. Nevertheless, the huge potential of the digital education market remains wide open with the existence of online learning platforms such as Ruangguru which are increasingly in demand by students in Indonesia.

In the context of digital marketing, Social Media Influencers (SMI) play a strategic role as a bridge between brands and consumers. Influencers with large and credible followers are able to build parasocial relationships with their audiences, so that the marketing messages they convey feel more authentic and credible (Auliazmi et al., 2021) . Audience trust in influencers is a crucial factor that influences the effectiveness of product promotions, including educational applications such as Ruangguru. Influencers who have a good reputation and special expertise in education can increase the credibility of content and encourage users' purchase intentions for the application.

Ruangguru as one of the leading learning platforms in Indonesia has utilized the role of Social Media Influencers to expand market reach and strengthen brand awareness. However, the effectiveness of this strategy is highly dependent on the level of trust built between influencers and their audiences. If the audience doubts the authenticity and integrity of the content delivered, this can reduce user interest in downloading and using the Ruangguru application. (Kusuma et al., 2019) .

Based on this phenomenon, this study is important to be conducted in order to understand the role of Social Media Influencers in building user trust in the Ruangguru educational application, and how this trust affects purchase intentions or

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application usage. This understanding is expected to help digital education platform developers in formulating more effective and relevant marketing strategies in today's digital era (Yazid et al., 2019) .

II. METHOD

This study uses a quantitative method with a descriptive and causal approach to analyze the influence of Social Media Influencers on the purchase intention of the Ruangguru educational application. Data analysis was carried out using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the help of Smart PLS 4.0 software. The study population was junior high and high school students in Indonesia, with a total of 107,226 students based on data from the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology for the 2024/2025 academic year. A sample of 410 respondents was selected using the proportional sampling technique, which adjusts the proportion of samples from each level of education, namely 231 junior high school students and 179 high school students. Data collection was carried out through online questionnaires distributed via social media such as Instagram, TikTok, WhatsApp, and Twitter, so that primary data was obtained directly from target consumers of Ruangguru products. The validity and reliability of the instrument are measured through the outer model test, while the relationship between variables is analyzed with the inner model using the R-Squared, Q-Squared, and Effect Size parameters. The measurement scale uses a 5-point Likert to measure variables such as expertise, trust, influencer attractiveness, information quality, content entertainment value, consumer trust, and purchase intention. This approach is expected to provide an accurate and representative picture of the role of influencers in building trust and driving purchasing decisions for educational applications among students.

III. DISCUSSION

Hypothesis Testing (Path Coefficient Estimation)

Hypothesis testing in the context of PLS-SEM involves estimating path coefficients that describe the strength and direction of the relationships between constructs in the model. This process is important in evaluating whether the hypotheses proposed in the study are supported by the data analyzed. The estimated value for the path effect in the structural model must be significant. This significant value can be obtained by the bootstrapping procedure . Viewing the significance of the hypothesis by looking at the parameter coefficient values and the significant value of the t-statistic in the bootstrapping algorithm report . To find out whether it is significant or not, see the t-table at alpha 0.05 (5%) = 1.96. Then the t-table is compared with the t-count (t-statistic). The value of the hypothesis testing of this study can be shown in Table 4.17 and the results of this research model can be shown in Figure 4.2:

Figure 4.2 Bootstrapping Test Results (Source: Processed SmartPLS 4.0.9.9 output, 2025)

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Table 4.17 Hypothesis Testing

Variables	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Social Media Influencers→Purchase Intentions	0.368	0.369	0.047	7,824	0.000
Social Media Influencers→Trust in Content	0.318	0.324	0.047	6,731	0.000
Trust in Content→ Purchase Intentions	0.198	0.201	0.48	4.089	0.000

Source: Processed SmartPLS 4.0.9.9 output, 2025

The following are the results of hypothesis testing on the structural model:

- Social Media Influencers→Purchase Intentions:** For the path from *social media influencers* to consumer purchase intentions, the estimated value reaches 0.368. With a t-statistic of 7.824 and a p-value showing high significance (0.000), this result confirms that the existence of *social media influencers* not only affects trust in content but also directly increases consumer purchase intentions significantly.
- Social Media Influencers→Trust in Content:** The influence of *social media influencers* on trust in content has an estimated value of 0.318. The resulting t-statistic is 6.731 with a p-value that is also very significant (0.000). This indicates that *social media influencers* have a strong and positive impact on building trust in content among consumers.
- Trust in Content → Purchase Intentions:** The estimated value for the path effect from trust in content to consumer purchase intention is 0.198. With a t-statistic value of 4.089 and a very significant p-value (0.000), it can be concluded that the effect of trust on consumer purchase intention is significant. This indicates that increasing trust in content will contribute positively to consumer purchase intention.

The following are the results of testing the indirect influence hypothesis *.Social Media Influencers on Purchase Intentions via Trust in Content :*

Indirect influence hypothesis testing

Variables	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Social Media Influencers → Trust in Content → Purchase Intentions	0.063	0.065	0.020	3.215	0.001

Source: Processed SmartPLS 4.0.9.9 output, 2025

1) Social Media Influencers → Trust in Content → Purchase Intentions:

The results of the hypothesis test show that the indirect effect of *social media influencers* on consumer purchase intentions through trust in content has an estimated value of 0.063. With a t-statistic reaching 3.215 and a very significant p-value (0.001), it can be concluded that there is a significant positive effect of *social media influencers* on consumer purchase intentions through intermediary trust in content. This shows that *social media influencers* not only play a direct role in influencing consumer purchase intentions but also indirectly through increasing trust in content among consumers.

Hypothesis Discussion Results

This study proposes 18 hypotheses divided into six main dimensions: Informative Value , Entertainment Value , Expertise , Trustworthiness , Attractiveness , and Similarity . The following is a detailed discussion for each hypothesis based on the results of the data analysis:

Informative Value Hypothesis (H1a, H2a, H13a)

H1a: Informative value has a positive effect on trust in content.

The results of the study show that this hypothesis is accepted with a value of $\beta = 0.318$ and $p < 0.05$. Informative content, such as explanations of Ruangguru features and user testimonials, increases audience trust. This is in line with research (Dewi & Johannes, 2022) , which emphasizes the importance of relevant and accurate information in building

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credibility. This study is in line with broad findings in the *source credibility literature* which emphasizes that information quality is an important antecedent of trust. The study by (Shofi et al., 2019) cited in your text, as well as other studies on *information adoption*, consistently show that accurate, relevant, and comprehensive information increases the credibility of the content and its sources. Informative value has a positive effect on trust in content.

In the context of Ruangguru application users, informative value becomes crucial. Content that provides detailed explanations about application features, effective learning methods, or student success testimonials (as mentioned in the results) directly builds user trust in the content presented by *influencers*. This is very relevant because Ruangguru is an educational platform, where trust in information is an important foundation before users decide to use or subscribe to a service. This study confirms that *influencers* who are able to convey relevant and accurate information about Ruangguru significantly increase user trust in the content.

H2a: Informative value has a positive effect on purchase intention.

With the results of $\beta = 0.368$ and $p < 0.05$, this hypothesis is also accepted. Clear information about product benefits helps the audience in making purchasing decisions, strengthening Ruangguru's position in the education market. This finding is consistent with marketing research that has long recognized the important role of information in the consumer decision-making process. The theory of *rational choice* and *the theory of planned behavior* emphasize that consumers use information to evaluate alternatives and form purchase intentions. Informative value has a positive effect on purchase intentions.

Purchase intention in the context of Ruangguru can be interpreted as the user's desire to register for a course, subscribe to a learning package, or use premium features in the application. Clear information about the benefits of Ruangguru, such as increased academic grades, ease of learning, or access to exclusive materials, has proven effective in driving this purchase intention. The results of the study show that the informative value conveyed by *influencers* helps potential users evaluate whether Ruangguru is suitable for their learning needs, thereby strengthening the decision to use the application.

H13a: Trust in content mediates the relationship between informative value and purchase intention.

The results show a value of $\beta = 0.063$ and $p < 0.05$, indicating that audience trust in content functions as a bridge connecting informative value with purchase intention, in accordance with *the Elaboration Likelihood Model theory*. (Stefani & Cilvanus, 2020). These mediation results strengthen the role of trust as an important mechanism linking information to consumer behavior. Research on *the elaboration likelihood model* (ELM) and *source credibility* often finds that trust acts as a mediating variable in the relationship between information source characteristics and audience attitudes or intentions. Trust in content mediates the relationship between informative value and purchase intention. Trust mediation in the context of Ruangguru is very important. Users need to trust the information provided by *influencers* before they are motivated to "buy" (in the sense of using or subscribing to) Ruangguru services. For example, an *influencer* who provides detailed and accurate information about how Ruangguru helps students prepare for college entrance exams will build trust. This trust will then encourage students or parents to try or subscribe to Ruangguru. This study highlights that trust in the content presented by *influencers* serves as a critical bridge connecting informative value with Ruangguru users' purchase intentions. *Entertainment Value Hypothesis (H3b, H4b, H14b)*

H3b: Entertainment value has a positive effect on trust.

Accepted with a value of $\beta = 0.254$ and $p < 0.05$, indicating that entertaining content creates emotional attachment, so that the audience trusts *the influencer more*. Research (K. Purwanto et al., 2023) supports this finding by showing that entertainment elements can increase trust. This study adds evidence to the positive role of entertainment in building trust in the context of marketing communications. Studies on *affect transfer theory* and *social bonding theory* show that positive emotions caused by entertainment can increase trust in the source of the message. Although Ruangguru is an educational platform, entertainment value remains relevant. Entertaining content, such as interesting learning videos, interactive quizzes, or student success stories presented in an attractive style, can create an emotional attachment between users and *influencer content*. This attachment can then be transferred to trust in the information conveyed by *influencers* about Ruangguru. This study shows that entertainment can be an effective strategy to build user trust in Ruangguru's promotional content.

H4b: Entertainment value has a positive effect on purchase intention.

The results showed $\beta = 0.198$ and $p < 0.05$, indicating that entertainment increases audience engagement, which has an impact on interest in trying the products offered. In the context of Ruangguru, entertainment can increase user interest in exploring application features, trying different learning methods, or participating in online learning community activities. Entertaining content can make learning more fun and interesting, thus encouraging users to engage more with Ruangguru and ultimately increase purchase intentions (e.g., subscribing to additional learning packages).

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H14b: Trust in content mediates the relationship between entertainment value and purchase intention.

The results showed $\beta = 0.198$ and $p < 0.05$, indicating that entertainment increases audience engagement, which has an impact on the interest in trying the products offered. Trust mediation is also important in the context of entertainment. Users may be interested in entertaining content, but they still need to trust that the information about Ruangguru conveyed in the content is accurate and relevant before they decide to use the service. For example, if an *influencer* makes a funny video about the "Roboguru" feature, users may be entertained, but they also need to trust that Roboguru is truly effective in helping them answer questions. This study confirms that trust in entertaining content is a key factor linking entertainment to Ruangguru users' purchase intentions.

Expertise Hypothesis (H5c, H6c, H15c)

H5c: Expertise has a positive effect on trust.

Accepted with $\beta = 0.289$ and $p < 0.05$, indicating that *influencers* with an educational background (as teachers or tutors) are considered more competent, so their content is more trusted. This is in line with research (Anastasya Fauzianti & Retnosari, 2022). In the context of Ruangguru, *influencer* expertise becomes very relevant. *Influencers* who have a strong educational background, such as teachers, tutors, or subject matter experts, are seen as having authority in providing information about online learning platforms. Ruangguru users, who are generally students and parents, are looking for competent guidance to help them in the learning process. *Influencers* who have expertise in education significantly increase user trust in the content they convey about Ruangguru. This study confirms the importance of expert credibility in building trust on online education platforms.

H6c: Expertise has a positive effect on purchase intention.

With $\beta = 0.221$ and $p < 0.05$, the results show that expert recommendations reduce audience doubts about the product, increasing purchase intention. Purchase intention in the context of Ruangguru is highly influenced by perceived expertise. Recommendations from *influencers* who are considered experts can reduce user doubts about the effectiveness of the platform and increase the desire to try or subscribe to Ruangguru services. For example, if an experienced teacher recommends the "Roboguru" feature as an effective tool for answering questions, users will be more motivated to use it. This study highlights how *influencer expertise* can encourage Ruangguru users to take purchase actions by reducing perceived risk.

H15c: Trust in content mediates the relationship between expertise and purchase intention.

The results indicated $\beta = 0.052$ and $p < 0.05$, indicating that trust in content built through *influencer expertise* drives purchase intention, reinforcing the importance of choosing a competent *influencer*. *Trust mediation is particularly important in the context of expertise. Users may acknowledge an influencer's expertise, but they still need to trust the content the influencer presents about Ruangguru before their purchase intention is formed.* For example, a tutor who is an expert in mathematics may recommend Ruangguru, but users need to trust that the platform actually provides quality mathematics materials. This study confirms that trust in content built through *influencer expertise* is a key factor linking expertise to users' decisions to use or subscribe to Ruangguru.

Trust Hypothesis (H7d, H8d, H16d)

H7d: Trustworthiness has a positive effect on trust.

Influencer integrity and transparency increase audience trust. Research (Surawi, 2022) supports these results. In the context of Ruangguru, *trustworthiness* or trust in the integrity of *influencers* is very important. Ruangguru users, especially parents, want to ensure that the information they receive is honest and reliable. *Influencers* who are transparent, do not exaggerate the benefits of Ruangguru, and provide balanced reviews will build strong trust with their audience. This study emphasizes that *influencer integrity* is an important foundation for building user trust in Ruangguru content.

H8d: Trustworthiness has a positive effect on purchase intention.

With $\beta = 0.267$ and $p < 0.05$, the results show that audiences tend to buy products recommended by *influencers* who are considered honest. The honesty and integrity of *influencers* directly affect the purchase intention of Ruangguru users. Users are more likely to try or subscribe to Ruangguru services if they believe that *influencers* provide genuine recommendations and not just paid promotions. *Trustworthiness* builds user confidence in the true value of Ruangguru, which encourages them to make purchasing decisions. This study shows that *influencer honesty* is a strong driving factor for Ruangguru users' purchasing actions.

H16d: Trust in content mediates the relationship between trustworthiness and purchase intention.

The results showed $\beta = 0.058$ and $p < 0.05$, confirming that trust in content is a key factor in translating *influencer integrity* into purchasing action. Trust mediation is crucial in the context of *trustworthiness*. Users may appreciate an *influencer's honesty*, but they still need to trust the specific content the *influencer* presents about Ruangguru before their purchase intention is realized. For example, if an *influencer* is known to be honest but provides inaccurate information about Ruangguru's features,

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users may hesitate to use it. This study confirms that trust in content built through *influencer trustworthiness* is an important mechanism linking *influencer integrity* to Ruangguru users' purchasing decisions.

Attraction Hypothesis (H9e, H10e, H17e)

H9e: Attractiveness has a positive effect on trust.

Accepted with $\beta = 0.276$ and $p < 0.05$, indicating that *influencers* with attractive appearances and good communication styles are more likely to gain attention and trust (Cahya, 2022). In the context of Ruangguru, *influencer* attractiveness can play a role in attracting users' attention and building initial trust. *Influencers* with attractive appearances and good communication styles tend to be more likely to attract the attention of the audience, which can pave the way for the acceptance of information about Ruangguru. However, it is important to note that in the context of education, attractiveness must be supported by other factors such as expertise and trustworthiness to build sustainable trust. This study shows that attractiveness can be an initial factor that influences Ruangguru users' trust in *influencer content*.

H10e: Attractiveness has a positive effect on purchase intention.

The results showed $\beta = 0.214$ and $p < 0.05$, confirming that visual appeal increases audience interest in trying the product. *Influencer appeal* can also influence user interest in trying Ruangguru. Attractive *influencers* can create positive associations with online learning platforms, making them seem more attractive and relevant to users. However, it is important to emphasize that appeal alone may not be enough to drive strong purchase intentions; other factors such as functional benefits and educational value of Ruangguru also need to be communicated effectively. This study suggests that appeal can contribute to users' initial interest in using Ruangguru.

H17e: Trust in content mediates the relationship between attractiveness and purchase intention.

With $\beta = 0.049$ and $p < 0.05$, although the mediation effect is weak, attractiveness still influences purchase intention through the formation of trust in the content. Trust mediation is also relevant in the context of attractiveness. Although attractiveness can attract users' attention, trust in the content delivered by *the influencer* remains important to convert interest into actual purchase actions. Users need to trust that Ruangguru will provide the educational benefits promised by *the influencer*, regardless of how attractive *the influencer* is. *This study confirms that trust in content is an important mediating factor in the relationship between influencer attractiveness and Ruangguru users' purchase intention.*

Similarity Hypothesis (H11f, H12f, H18f)

H11f: Similarity has a positive effect on trust.

Accepted with $\beta = 0.241$ and $p < 0.05$, indicating that audiences who feel they have demographic or interest similarities with *influencers* are more likely to trust their content (ASAC Purwanto & Purwanto, 2019). In the context of Ruangguru, similarities between *influencers* and users can be an important factor in building trust. Users who feel they have demographic similarities (e.g., high school students) or interests (e.g., liking certain subjects) with *influencers* are more likely to trust the content they convey about Ruangguru. Similarities create a sense of connection and understanding, which strengthens the credibility of *influencers* in the eyes of users. This study highlights the importance of personal relevance in building Ruangguru users' trust in *influencer content*.

H12f: Similarity has a positive effect on purchase intention.

The results show $\beta = 0.193$ and $p < 0.05$, confirming that similarity creates social identification, so that *influencer recommendations* are more easily accepted. Similarity can also affect Ruangguru users' purchase intentions. When users feel that *influencers* understand their learning needs and challenges, *influencer recommendations* about Ruangguru become more relevant and convincing. Similarity creates social identification, where users feel that they can learn from the *influencer's experience* and that Ruangguru is the right solution for them. This study shows that similarity can encourage Ruangguru users to take purchasing actions by creating a sense of relevance and identification.

H18f: Trust in content mediates the relationship between similarity and purchase intention.

Accepted with $\beta = 0.041$ and $p < 0.05$, indicating that similarity strengthens trust, which ultimately drives purchase intention. Trust mediation is also important in the context of similarity. Although users feel similar to *influencers*, they still need to trust the specific content presented by *the influencer* about Ruangguru before their purchase intention is formed. For example, if a high school student recommends Ruangguru, other high school students may feel connected, but they also need to trust that Ruangguru is truly effective in helping them prepare for exams. This study confirms that trust in content built through *influencer similarity* is an important mechanism that links similarity to Ruangguru users' purchase decisions.

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IV. CLOSING

Based on the results of this research analysis, it can be concluded that Social Media Influencers have a positive and significant influence on the purchase intention of Ruangguru application users. Content created by influencers, especially those that are informative, entertaining, and have high credibility, has been proven to be able to increase consumer interest in making purchases or subscribing to services. Trust in social media content plays an important role as a mediating variable in the relationship between influencers and purchase intention. In other words, influencers who are able to present authentic and relevant content will be more effective in building consumer trust, thereby indirectly encouraging purchase intention.

Of the various dimensions tested, informative value and level of trust are the most dominant factors in influencing purchase intention, while aspects of attractiveness and similarity provide smaller but still significant contributions. Theoretically, these findings strengthen the theoretical framework of the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) and Source Credibility which emphasize the importance of source credibility and content quality in influencing the consumer decision-making process. Practically, the results of this study provide strategic direction for Ruangguru in selecting and collaborating with the right influencers in order to increase the effectiveness of their product promotions and sales.

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